

PRAGMATIC AND LINGVOCULTURAL CONTEXT OF SPEECH ACTS

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Annotation. This article is devoted to some issues related to the problems of “respect” in communication and its role in sociolinguistics as one of the types of speech act. And also, the specific linguistic feature of each means, i.e. its similarities and differences with other means in the field, is divided into lexical-thematic groups.

Key words: concept, linguistics, language, nation, communication, interact, addressee, respect, language means, phenomena.

The field of linguistics is increasingly focusing on how language units relate to human factors. Historically, linguistic expressions of respect have been categorized based on the target individual (e.g., women, men, children). This categorization suggests a functional-pragmatic classification of these linguistic resources. Socio-economic and political changes directly influence a language's vocabulary, leading to the introduction of new concepts, terms, and expressions. Consequently, research is now emphasizing the pragmatic and cultural aspects of language, particularly how expressions of "respect" are represented and evolve within these dynamic processes.

The relation of language phenomena to the social factor is established by European linguists [21.22]. Later, to this phenomenon was paid attention in Russian and Uzbek linguistics. Views were expressed on the role of addressing and honour in the speech process in the works of such scientists as N.I.Filicheva, A.A.Ufimtseva, N.Khomsky, G.S.Shchur, A.Vezhbitskaya, V.V.Babaytseva, N.S.Valgina, V.V.Kolesov [19.18.20.23.3.4.1.12.2.11]. The role of gestures in the process of addressing and addressing in children's language is studied in the dissertation of A.G.Gadjieva [5].

While the social significance of addressing in relation to dialogic speech was studied by H.Doniyorov, B.Yuldashev, form of addressing, communication etiquette and stable speech habits were studied by S.Muminov, Sh. Rahmatullaev compared the existing forms of addressing in Uzbek with those in Russian [6].

The application of the concept of syntactic field in grammar is artificially (theoretically) associated with attempts to model the relationships between syntactic structures that actually exist in the minds of language users. In the division of syntactic fields it is necessary to have a set of linguistic means that are expressively different, but partially or completely consistent in the content plan, that is, have common invariant semantic features. Also, semantic invariance, functional closeness, leads to a functionally collaborative relationship in a particular syntactic field. The approximate syntactic models in the field plan form a field and serve the general area of the language. It is well known that in the semantic field words do not enter into internal relations and connections as a whole with the sum of all their fields, but with their separate meanings. Meaning can be viewed as a differential-semantic feature of words or a set of components. In solving the problem of the semantic connection of words in the field, it is necessary to consider the following: if the meanings of the words have a common part (the sets intersect), the two words are considered to be related to each other. In this case, the meanings in the semantic field must be interspersed with the general components, i.e., the parts that are in zero, equivalent, and specific opposition. If the relationship between the sets corresponds to four types of opposition, then the opposition between the elements of the set is only zero and disjunctive. In semantic fields, the relationship of polysemantic word meanings has a special place. It is now said that polysemous word meanings form an interconnected and interdependent

microsystem, and that within a polysemous word there can also be semantic homonymy, i.e., meanings that are not part of a common semantic [8. 9].

F.A.Litvin argues that the meanings of polysemantic words can include the following three types of relationships: intersection, addition, semantic homonymy [13]. It should be noted that only intersecting and joining relations unite meanings into one semantic field. Semantic homonymy, on the other hand, divides itself into different areas. Accordingly, Professor Sh. Iskandarova says that the relationship of intersection and joining is important for the study of polysemous words as a semantic structure of the field, the “scope of concepts”. The polysemy of a word, both through its basic meaning and in its addition, always lies at the center of the semantic field they create, and all other meanings are directly or indirectly subordinated to it. Although the proposal to take its main meaning as a semantic invariant of a polysemous word among the explanations of common meanings is introduced by most scholars, it is only one of the lexical-semantic variants of the word and its use in speech negates other variants [8. 9].

E.V.Kuznetsova examining the lexicon of the verb, the invariant of the polysemous word suggests that it be called a generalized meaning, considering it necessary to obtain a separate modification of it rather than a simple general meaning as a semantic standard.

Generalized meaning is the basic specific meanings that arise on the basis of the development of their content in a given situation. General meaning as a separate lexical-semantic variant differs from the main meaning in terms of semantic structure and text type (general meaning occurs in a broader text than the specific meaning), and differs from other secondary meanings in its proximity to the main definite meaning and its special role in the secondary synonymous paradigm. The peculiarity of the semantic fields that make up the meanings of a polysemous word is that they relate to a single word as a unit of expression plan. But with the means of the plan of expression, the particular meanings of the polysemous word must also be differentiated. The main means of this distinction is text [12].

We know that every work of art brings with it many innovations in our spiritual life. They teach the reader a new look at what is going on in life, arming him with a new idea. Everyone expresses their opinion differently. By saying this “new word or phrase”, he realizes his purpose through the existing lexical-expressive means. But any new meaning does not always lead to the emergence of new words, phrases, expressive structures. However, as a result of various research, new words or new content can be discovered on their own. These are traditional means of artistic representation, which help to accurately embody in the imagination of the reader-listener the quality, character, shape and style of the created image or scenery.

There are also linguistic means used in relation to a person in power, which are among the sentences that form the basis for a secondary nomination. First of all, respect should be distinguished from flattery. Because they can be positive or negative. Respect is positive, for all languages have a set of means that make up a particular system. We called that set of linguistic means as the semantic field. Ниҳоят, Улуғбек қиличи ўткир чиқиб, мағрибдан машрикқача қанот ёзган ҳудудсиз салтанат хиёл осойиш топган эди, тожу тахт валиаҳди шаҳзода Абдуллатиф ўз падари бузрукворига қарши шамшир кўтариб чиқди. (*Eventually, Ulugbek's sword came out sharp, and the boundless kingdom, which spread its wings from west to east, found peace*). Ражаб ойининг бошларида аълоҳазратлари лашкар тортиб Жайхун томон отланишга мажбур бўлди (At the beginning of the month of Rajab, His Majesty was forced to draw an army and march towards Jaihun. Аммо давлатпаноҳ Жайхун бўйларида лашкар тортиб турганида дорулмулкда содир бўлган фитналар уни Самарқандга қайтишга мажбур этди [7]. (*However, when the state was drawing troops to the shores of Ceyhan, the conspiracies in Dorulmulk forced him to return to Samarkand*).

Differences in the habit of communication between women and men are observed at almost all levels of the language system. Firstly, we will talk about the units in the stages of the communication process.

Ancient Turkic peoples considered treating one's name with respect a sign of respect and esteem for that person. The main way of such respect is not to call a person by name. Accordingly,

among most of the Turkic peoples, there were customs that young people could not call the elderly people by their names, and the wife could not name the husband, and the husband could not name the wife. Such a custom, especially for women, was strictly adhered to in terms of etiquette. For example, in the past, in many families in Fergana, it is still common for a woman to call her husband by the name of one of her children (mostly the eldest child) and to use expressions such as “my son’s father”, “my husband”, “my master”. When a husband speaks of his wife, it is accustomed that he uses the words such as “your bride”, “your daughter”, “your sister”, and “my family”. “It’s very common in many nations around the world, including Armenians and Koreans, Georgians and Azerbaijanis, Kazakhs and Turkmens” [14].

Ҳаммаёқ қий-чув бўлиб кетди.

- Худога топширдим, болам!

- Тезроқ келинг, دادаси [24].

(There was a commotion everywhere.

“I trust you to God, my son!”

“Come quickly, the father”.)

In this example, we see respect for a man by a woman referring to her husband as “*the father*” (*دادаси*).

- Бизни кутдирма, ўғлим.

Отабек мағлуб бир боқиш билан бу сўзни айтқучи отасига қаради ва ялинчоқ бир оҳангда жавоб берди:

- Мен сизларнинг орзуларингизни бажаришига агар хурсандчилигингиз шу билан бўлса ҳар вақт ҳозирман. Аммо бир бечорага кўра-била туриб жабр ҳам хиёнат... Ҳожи ўғлининг мақсадига дарров тушуна олмади ва сўради:

- Кимга, хотининггами?

- Йўқ, сизнинг оладирган келинингизга. Ўғлингизнинг вужуди билан орзуингизни қондириш осон бўлса ҳам келинингиз қаришида мени бир жонсиз ҳайкал ўрнида тасаввур қилингиз [25].

(“Don’t keep us waiting, my son”).

Otabek looked at his father, who said this with a defeated look, and replied in a begging tone:

- I am always ready to fulfill your dreams - if you are happy with it. But clear oppression towards a poor person is also a betrayal ...

Haji could not immediately understand his son's purpose and asked:

“To whom, your wife?”

“No, to your soon-to-be bride”. Imagine me instead of a lifeless statue in front of your bride, even if it is easy to fulfill your dream with your son’s body).

However, in this example, the word “your bride” shows Otabek's indifference to Zaynab.

In conclusion, the national mentality, communicative style, politeness norms, and cultural uniqueness of Uzbek and English cultures shape how speakers influence listeners in communication. Speech etiquette plays a crucial role in conveying respect within these interactions.

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